

Intellectual
Property
Office

Application

GB2611463.7

Application details

Application number	GB2611463.7
Application title	M.A.R.S. Companion (Mobile Autonomous Reasoning System): Portable Offline Voice Assistant with Sequential Resource Orchestration and Semantic Memory Retrieval
Status	Filed

Dates

Lodged date	15 May 2026
Filing date	15 May 2026

Applicants

Name	Address
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